

Oximates and Diethylhydroxylamines of Antimony(III)

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Ethyl antimonite reacts with oximes and diethylhydroxylamine to give complexes of the general formula $(EtO)_{3-n}Sb(L)_n$ (where $n=1-3$; $LH=$ oximes or diethylhydroxylamine). These derivatives are thermally stable and can be distilled unchanged under reduced pressure. The mixed ethoxide acetoximate derivatives readily interchange their ethoxy contents with other alkoxy groups when treated with alcohols. The reaction of triacetoximate with acetyl chloride in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios yields mono- and di-chloride antimony acetoximate respectively. Trisoximates have been shown to undergo readily insertion reactions with phenyl isocyanate. Attempts have been made to throw light on the nature of the products by their ir spectra and molecular weights in benzene.

DURING the last decade, oxime derivatives of Al(III), Ti(IV)¹ and Sn(IV)²⁻⁵ as well as several alkoxides of Sb(III) & (V) and their derivatives⁶⁻⁹ have been patented; some of these are reported to be of industrial importance¹⁻⁹ and useful as fungicides, bactericides, flame retarding additives, polymerisation catalysts, etc. Except for a reference to triphenylantimony oximate in a recent publication¹⁰, no work appears to have been described on compounds containing Sb-O-N bonds either in academic or in patent literature.

In the present communication, we report the reactions of ethyl antimonite with a number of oximes and with diethylhydroxylamine. The reactions were carried out in anhydrous benzene; the ethanol produced during the reaction was azeotroped out and estimated to check the progress of the reaction.

Experimental

Ethyl antimonite was prepared by the sodium method¹¹ and distilled before use. Oximes were prepared by standard methods. Diethylhydroxylamine was dried by storage over KOH (5-6 hr) followed by distillation (77-79°/ca 40 mm) over KOH and aluminium isopropoxide respectively. All solvents were dried and distilled before use. Reactions were carried out under rigorously anhydrous conditions.

Antimony and nitrogen were estimated as antimony pyrogallate¹² and by Kjeldahl method respectively. Ethanol was estimated by oxidation with normal dichromate solution in 12.5% sulphuric acid.¹³ Chlorine was estimated as silver chloride.

Molecular weights were determined in a semi-micro ebulliometer (GALLENKAMP) using a thermistor sensing. Infrared spectra of these derivatives were recorded as neat using KBr optics (Perkin-Elmer 337) in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Reactions

Reaction of ethyl antimonite with oximes and diethylhydroxylamine:

Calculated quantities of oxime (acetoxime, ethylmethylketoxime, diethylketoxime or cyclopentanone oxime) or diethylhydroxylamine were added to ethylantimonite in benzene and the mixture was refluxed for ca 4-5 hours. The binary azeotrope was distilled off at 68-80°C, followed by excess benzene. The residual solvent was removed under reduced pressure ca 40°/1 mm. Results of these reactions are summarised in table 1.

Reactions of Antimony(III) trichloride and acetoxime in 1:3 molar ratio:

Mixture of acetoxime (9.92g) and triethylamine (13.7g) in benzene (40 ml) was added to antimony trichloride (10.32g) in benzene (30 ml) at -0°C. The mixture was kept overnight and then refluxed for ca 3-4 hours. Triethylaminehydrochloride (19.9g) formed during the reaction was separated out by filtering the mixture in cold. From the filtrate, excess of the solvent was then removed under reduced pressure (-40°/1 mm) to give a liquid (15.3g) which was purified by distillation (122°-3°/0.2 mm; 7.6g; yield=50%). Found: Sb, 36.1; N=12.9; $Sb(ONCMe_2)_3$ requires: Sb, 36.0; N=12.4%. $Sb(ONCMeEt)_3$ was also similarly prepared. Found: Sb, 31.8; N=11.1; $Sb(ONCMeEt)_3$ requires: Sb, 32.0; N, 11.0%.

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF ETHYLANTIMONITE WITH OXIMES AND DIETHYLHYDROXYLAMINE

Compd. No.	Sb (OEt) ₃	Reactants (g) R:NOH	Molar Ratio	Products	B.P.	% Yield	Nature	Alcohol liberated (g) Found (Calc.)	Analysis (%)		Mol. Wt. Found (Calc.)	i.r. assignments C=N (N-O)* (cm ⁻¹)
									(1)-(3) R=Me ₂ C	(4)-(6) R=Me(Et)C		
1.	3.01	0.85	1:1	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ON:CMe ₂)	72°/0.1mm	90	Yellow liquid	0.45 (0.54)	43.1 (42.9)	5.1 (4.9)	300 (284)	1625 w, 1640 w
2.	3.24	1.84	1:2	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ON:CMe ₂) ₂	110°/0.3mm	84	"	1.08 (1.16)	39.1 (39.1)	8.9 (9.0)	318 (311)	1625 w, 1638 w
3.	2.37	2.00	1:3	Sb(ON:CMe ₂) ₃	122°/0.2mm	60	"	1.23 (1.28)	35.9 (36.0)	12.2 (12.4)	338 (338)	1620 m, 1645 m
4.	3.77	1.28	1:1	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ON:CMeEt)	105°/0.2mm	85	"	0.59 (0.68)	41.2 (40.85)	4.7 (4.7)	335 (298)	1625 m, 1640 m
5.	3.21	2.17	1:2	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ON:CMeEt) ₂	130°/0.2mm	78	"	1.01 (1.15)	35.8 (35.9)	8.6 (8.3)	385 (339)	1625 m, 1645 m
6.	2.69	2.74	1:3	Sb(ON:CMeEt) ₃	145°/0.2mm	70	"	1.34 (1.45)	31.8 (32.0)	11.0 (11.05)	383 (380)	1625 m, 1650 m
7.	2.89	1.14	1:1	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ON:CEt ₂)	135°/0.3mm	70	"	0.43 (0.51)	38.9 (39.0)	4.5 (4.5)	320 (312)	1630 w, 1655 vw
8.	2.33	1.83	1:2	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ON:CEt ₂) ₂	140°/0.2mm	72	"	0.75 (0.84)	33.1 (33.15)	7.9 (7.6)	380 (367)	1630 m, 1655 sh
9.	2.11	2.50	1:3	Sb(ON:CEt ₂) ₃	149°/0.3mm	77	"	1.00 (1.14)	28.2 (28.8)	10.1 (9.95)	420 (422)	1620 w, 1655 vw
10.	2.67	1.02	1:1	(EtO) ₂ Sb[ON:C(CH ₂) ₃ CH ₂]	73°/0.3mm	50	Brown liquid	0.48 (0.48)	39.8 (39.25)	4.5 (4.5)	318 (310)	1620 - 1640 w(b)
11.	2.39	1.84	1:2	(EtO) ₂ Sb[ON:C(CH ₂) ₃ CH ₂] ₂	97°/0.3mm	28	"	0.81 (0.86)	33.4 (33.5)	7.7 (7.7)	369 (363)	1635 w, 1645 m
12.	2.32	2.68	1:3	Sb[ON:C(CH ₂) ₃ CH ₂] ₃	Decomposes	—	"	1.08 (1.25)	29.45 (29.25)	10.1 (10.1)	429 (416)	1630 w, 1665 w
13.	2.01	0.70	1:1	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ON:Et ₂)	90°/0.2mm	78	Yellow liquid	0.35 (0.36)	40.5 (40.6)	4.6 (4.6)	334 (300)	918 w, 950 s, 958 s
14.	2.73	1.89	1:2	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ONEt ₂) ₂	100°/0.3mm	75	"	0.89 (0.98)	35.5 (35.5)	8.0 (8.2)	352 (343)	908 sh, 922 w, 955s
15.	2.47	2.57	1:3	Sb(ONEt ₂) ₃	105°/0.3mm	68	"	1.26 (1.33)	32.0 (31.5)	10.8 (10.9)	385 (386)	908 vs, 922 s, 948s

* s=strong; m=medium; w=weak; sh=shoulder; b=broad

TABLE 2—INTERCHANGE REACTIONS OF DIETHOXY MONOACETOXIMATE WITH ALCOHOLS

Compd. No.	Reactants	Grams	Products	B.P.	% Yield	Nature	Alcohol liberated (g) Found (Calc.)	Analysis (%)		Mol. wt. Found (Calc.)	i.r. assignments C=N (cm ⁻¹)
								(Pr ^t O) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)	(Bu ^t O) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)		
1.	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)	1.28 excess	(Pr ^t O) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)	78-80°/0.3mm	50	Colourless liquid	—	39.3 (39.0)	4.5 (4.5)	339 (312)	1630 w, 1665 w
2.	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)	1.51 excess	(Bu ^t O) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)	85°/0.2mm	60	"	0.46 (0.49)	35.0 (35.8)	3.9 (4.1)	350 (340)	1620 w, 1640 w
3.	(EtO) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)	1.10 excess	(Amt ^t O) ₂ Sb(ONCMMe ₂)	78-80°/0.1mm	60	"	—	33.1 (33.1)	3.7 (3.8)	382 (368)	1620 w(b), 1640 w

Interchange Reactions with alcohols :

Excess of isopropanol, tert. butanol, or tert-amyl alcohol was added to antimony diethoxy monoacetoximate and the mixture was refluxed for about 4-5 hr. The azeotrope followed by excess of benzene was collected. Excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure (~40°/1 mm). Reactions are summarised in Table 2.

Reaction between Antimony triacetoximate and Acetylchloride :

(a) *In 1:1 molar ratio :* Antimony triacetoximate (1.36 g) in benzene (20 ml), cooled to 0°-5°, was treated with acetyl chloride (0.316 g) and was kept at room temperature (~28°C) for 12 hours or heated at 80° for about one hour. Finally, the product was completely precipitated out by adding n-hexane to the solution. After filtration, the compound was dried at ~40°/0.5 mm to give a yellow solid (1.1 g) Found : Sb, 41.0 ; N, 9.2 ; Cl, 11.4 ; ClSb(ONCMe₂)₂ requires : Sb, 40.4 ; Cl, 11.8 ; N, 9.3%.

(b) *In 1:2 molar ratio :* Acetyl chloride (1.02 g) was added to antimony-triacetoximate (2.21 g) in benzene (about 20 ml) cooled to 0°-5° and the mixture was then refluxed for about 3-4 hours. Excess solvent was decanted out and the brown sticky solid (2.2 g) was then dried at 40°-50°/0.5 mm. Found : Sb, 32.3 ; Cl, 18.7 ; N, 7.3, Cl₂Sb(ONCMe₂) (Me₂CNOOCMe) requires : Sb, 32.1 ; Cl, 18.7 ; N, 7.4%.

Reactions of antimony trisoximates with phenylisocyanate :

Antimony trisacetoximate (0.90 g) in benzene (~20 ml) was treated with phenylisocyanate (0.95 g) and was refluxed for about half an hour. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give red viscous solid (1.85 g). Found : Sb, 17.3 ; N, 11.9 ;

Similarly prepared was Sb(N $\begin{array}{c} \text{Ph} \\ | \\ \text{O} \\ || \\ \text{C} \end{array}$ ONCMeEt)₃ Found : Sb, 16.6 ; N, 11.3 ; requires : Sb, 16.5 ; N, 11.4%.

Results and Discussion

It has been found that when ethyl antimonite is treated with these ligands in different stoichiometric ratios, the reactions proceed smoothly and the corresponding mono, di-, or tri-oximates or diethylhy-

droxylaminates are formed quantitatively by simple reactions :

(where R¹=Me and Et ; R²=Me and Et and n=1-3)

Antimony trisoximates were also synthesised by the reaction of SbCl₃ with oximes in presence of triethylamine :

Antimony diethoxy monoacetoximate was treated with excess isopropanol, ter-butanol, or ter-amyl alcohol in benzene. The replacement of both the ethoxy group was quite facile :

Oximates and diethylhydroxylaminates of antimony (III) are all colourless or yellow liquids and can be distilled in vacuo with the exception of the triscyclopentanone oximate which appears to undergo decomposition. These derivatives have been found to be soluble in common organic solvents like benzene, chloroform, etc. but these are instantaneously hydrolysed by water. Molecular weight determinations suggest that these derivatives are monomeric in boiling benzene.

Attempts have been made to synthesise some chloride oximates of antimony. Antimony trisacetoximate has been treated with acetyl chloride in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratio. The reaction is exothermic and can be represented by the following equations :

These chloride acetoximates, on being heated in sealed capillary tubes, did not melt sharply but appear to undergo decomposition.

Antimony trisoximates in benzene solution were treated with phenylisocyanate and the progress of the reaction was followed by the disappearance of the N=C=O band (2275-2250 cm^{-1}) and the appearance of a new strong absorption band (1715 \pm 5 cm^{-1}) due to the group (C=O) in the i.r. spectrum

where $\text{R}^1 = \text{Me}$; $\text{R}^2 = \text{Me}$ and Et

I.r. spectra: The infrared spectra of oximates of Sb(III) show two weak bands at 1650 \pm 10 cm^{-1} and 1625 \pm 5 cm^{-1} in the C=N absorption range¹⁴. There is a lowering of about 40-50 cm^{-1} in the C=N stretching vibrations (occurring at 1625 \pm 5 cm^{-1}). Compared to C=N stretching vibrations (1668 \pm 10 cm^{-1}) observed in free oximes¹⁴. As discussed in earlier communication on tantalum¹⁵, this might indicate some association of these derivatives also in the liquid state, through "MON-MON" types¹⁶⁻²⁰ of bridges, although measurements of molecular weights indicate that they exist as monomers in boiling benzene. It appears, therefore, that the strength

of the bridge (SbON-SbON) is not sufficient to prevent its depolymerisation at refluxing benzene temperature¹⁶⁻²⁰.

The diethylhydroxylamine derivatives show intense absorption in the region 955-908 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to $\sqrt{\text{N-O}}$ stretching mode. The corresponding $\sqrt{\text{N-O}}$ in the ligand²¹, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NOH}$, is observed at 912 cm^{-1} . It appears that there is an increase in $\sqrt{\text{N-O}}$ stretching vibrations in these derivatives.

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